

Al-Khayran: A Pre-Pottery Neolithic B Site in the West-Central Transjordanian Highlands

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Abstract: Reconstructions of the emergence of primarily agricultural economies in Southwest Asia have largely focused on data derived from village sites containing multiple households. This article presents the results of excavations at Pre-Pottery Neolithic B al-Khayran in the west-central Transjordanian Highlands. The site consists of a single substantially built square habitation structure, as well as associated refuse deposits. Results demonstrate that the site was occupied by a residential unit enacting a typical suit of household activities, including cereal production. This shows that there was greater variability in the occupational behaviors of agricultural producers during this time period than has previously been reported. Additionally, results from al-Khayran allow us to specify subsistence production behaviors that are not visible at village sites. The potential logistical and socio-cultural dynamics that drove the economic and residential practices of al-Khayran’s inhabitants are discussed.

Keywords: Pre-Pottery Neolithic B, Southern Levant, al-Khayran, agricultural economies, settlement systems

Introduction

This article presents preliminary results from excavations at the early Neolithic (Table 1) settlement of al-Khayran. Al-Khayran is located on the southern ridge of Wadi ‘Assal in the west-central Transjordanian Highlands – a portion of the southern Levantine Mediterranean zone (Fig. 1). It consists of a single structure constructed and reconstructed in two phases, as well as associated refuse dating to the Pre-Pottery Neolithic B (PPNB). Knapped stone technology and formal tool types at the site include bidirectional cores (Quintero and Wilke 1995; Barzilai 2010) and Helwan, Jericho, and Byblos points (Gopher 1994; Shea 2013) (Fig. 2). Architectural morphology (Flannery 1972), construction methods (Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2013), and materials (Clarke 2012), being square dry-stacked stone architecture with lime plaster features (Fig. 3), align with residential structures of the PPNB in the region.

The excavations at al-Khayran are part of a wider research program focusing on how the emergence of agricultural economies restructured the relations of production within subsistence systems. Research has shown that there are barriers to the development of economies focused primarily on agriculture, even in communities that practice the husbandry of domesticated plants and animals (Hunn and Williams 1982; Rowley-Conwy and Layton 2011; Bulbeck 2013; Denham and Donohue 2022). These barriers include the high labor costs of husbandry as compared to foraging (Sahlins 1972; Bowles 2011; Reyes-García 2019; but see Kraft *et al.* 2021) and the

uneven temporal access to harvests created by delayed return economies (Woodburn 1982). However, scholars have identified ways in which these challenges can be overcome, mostly focused on the intensification of subsistence production (Boserup 1965; Morrison 1994) allowing for higher productivity and more even access to food (Halstead and O’Shea 1989).

Period	Dates cal. BCE
Pre-Pottery Neolithic A (PPNA)	9750-8500
Early Pre-Pottery Neolithic B (EPPNB)	8500-8250
Middle Pre-Pottery Neolithic B (MPPNB)	8250-7500
Late Pre-Pottery Neolithic B (LPPNB)	7500-7000
Final Pre-Pottery Neolithic B / Pre-Pottery Neolithic C (FPPNB / PPNC)	7000-6400

Table 1 Early Neolithic chronology in the Southern Levant (Birkenfeld *et al.* 2024).

Additionally, innovative uses of space and mobility, due to their greater flexibility than the material properties of subsistence systems (Blaikie 1971), are a favored means of overcoming the challenges associated with developing primarily agricultural economies. A simple example of this is when arable land is the most important and/ or scarcest resource, producers will locate their residences within fields, leading to settlement dispersal (Demangeon 1962; Chisholm 1979; Stone 1996). However, if resources necessary for production must be acquired through social interactions, such as labor recruitment or specialist-produced tools, then settlement aggregation is a common response as it allows producers efficient access to the provisioners of their

needed resources (Christaller 1966; Stone 1996). In cases where both of these pressures exist, producers can develop a variety of responses that fall under the rubric of satellite settlements. These can range from simple features that facilitate in-field intensification to a dual residence pattern, where farmers may split their time between primary residences in aggregated settlements and in-field residences that are occupied during periods of high subsistence labor demands (Sutton 1977; Ward 1978; Chisholm 1979; Moore 1979; Preucel 1990; Stone 1996).

Fig. 1 Map of the Southern Levant with al-Khayran marked (Drawing: M. Kroot, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

Other researchers have emphasized the social barriers to the development of primarily agricultural economies. Bowles and Choi (2013) note that food-sharing practices common in many small-scale societies disincentivize the husbandry of resources. This is because the redistribution of outputs greatly reduces any potential benefits for individuals who incur the high costs of agricultural intensification. Similarly, relations of production that prevent transgenerational control of subsistence production

loci discourage intensification through investments in landesque capital. Production units are typically intergenerational and thus, those who bear the cost of such investments will lose their benefits eventually when they do not inherit the means of production into which they have invested (Goody 1972). In both of these cases, in order for primarily agricultural production systems to develop, there must be a concomitant shift in the relations of production that increases access to subsistence goods for individual producers, such as private land-holding (Bowles and Choi 2013; Gallagher *et al.* 2015) and/ or inter-generational inheritance of the means of production (Shenk *et al.* 2010).

Fig. 2 Examples of chronologically diagnostic knapped stone artifacts recovered at al-Khayran. A bidirectional core, B-C tanged points, D side-notched point. (Drawings: M. Kroot and S.M. Konecki-Brazeal, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

Fig. 3 Photo of the eastern wall of the earlier phase of the structure at al-Khayran. (Photo: M. Kroot, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

These models are relevant to the PPNB of the Southern Levant because villages of the region’s Mediterranean zone are among the earliest in the world to present many of the classic traits of village-based agricultural communities (Banning 1998, 2012; Bar-Yosef 2001; Kuijt and Goring-Morris 2002; Simmons 2007; Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2020). The essential elements of this characterization are

aggregation into substantially sized residential agglomerations, sedentary habitation segmented along familial lines in durable architecture, and a primarily agricultural economy featuring the husbandry of domesticated plants and animals. Additionally, during this period, a number of analyses suggest the possibility that subsistence products were privately held by households based on the location of storage (Flannery 1972, 2002; Byrd 1994; Kuijt 2000, 2008, 2015) and food preparation features (Wright 2000) within residential architecture. There is also evidence of potential changes in the relations of production in other areas of economic behavior, such as the development of household-based specialized production (Quintero and Wilke 1995; Rollefson and Parker 2002; Jensen 2008; Barzilai 2010; Gebel 2010).

However, our current evidence does not represent the totality of changes to subsistence systems, as it does not directly address production practices and how they articulate with economic systems. This is an important issue given that food storage and preparation practices in smallholder farming communities are not always enacted by the same social units as subsistence production behavior (see examples in Douglass and Gonlin 2012; Fogle *et al.* 2015; Netting *et al.* 1984). Because al-Khayran presents evidence of substantial subsistence production behavior, data from the site can help us construct models of how production units organized and enacted their in-field subsistence behaviors. Additionally, it can help us understand the broader constellation of economic relations that connect production practices to larger community social structures.

Methods

Al-Khayran was first identified within the international archaeological community through a survey directed by Jacobs (1983). Based on the presence of formal tool types typical of the Pre-Pottery Neolithic illustrated in the survey results, an intensive study of the early Neolithic component of the site and its context within the surrounding region was initiated. To develop a detailed understanding of the extent of surface remains and their implications for site dating and excavation methods, a set of 10m² dog leash surface collection units were systematically placed across al-Khayran at 15m intervals. Results identified PPNB artifacts, including Helwan points and bidirectional cores and blades, over an area of approximately 0.38ha, measuring *c.* 80m E-W and *c.* 60m N-S (Fig. 4).

Based on these results, a series of 2 x 1m test excavation units were dug at 20m intervals with the goal of identifying the extent of subsurface deposits. Only a single unit in the southwestern portion of the

surface scatter returned subsurface archaeological materials. Horizontal excavations were expanded outwards from this singular test unit in 1 x 1m squares with the goals of determining the edges and depths of subsurface deposits, identifying and characterizing remains of the built environment and activity areas, and recovering artifacts in association with their architectural, activity area, and stratigraphic contexts. Excavation units were expanded in all directions until no subsurface artifacts were identified for two consecutive units in each of the four cardinal directions. Balks were left unexcavated every 4m (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4 Results of systematic surface collection at al-Khayran. (Drawing: M. Kroot and E. Wallace, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

Fig. 5 Map of excavation grid at al-Khayran with surface collection and excavation results. (Drawing: M. Kroot and E. Wallace, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

All deposits were screened using 2mm mesh and dug within depositional layers, divided into 10cm levels for those strata greater than 0.1m in depth. Digging continued downward until 0.2m of deposits devoid of artifacts and architectural features were excavated. All knapped stones, ground stones, fauna, and small finds identified in screened deposits were collected and analyzed. Where appropriate, scientific samples were taken, including radiocarbon, phytolith, spherulite, pollen, and macro-botanical remains, and submitted for specialized analyses.

When architecture was identified, interior and exterior deposits were treated as separate loci, regardless of their position relative to unit boundaries. Additionally, when interior and exterior surfaces were encountered, the 0.05m of deposits overlying them were treated as separate loci from overlying deposits, whether or not a stratigraphic change could be identified during excavation. Once the full extent of the built environment, including structures and prepared surfaces, was identified, particular materials, such as macro- and micro-botanical remains, *in situ* artifacts, and complete activity areas, were targeted, leading to various specific excavation choices, such as the excavation of balks and deposit sampling, that deviated from typical practices. Most of the interior and exterior surfaces of the later phase of the structure were excavated. In the southeastern quarter of the structure, excavations continued past the floor surface of the later phase, ultimately reaching the floor of the earlier phase of the structure and continuing below.

Fig. 6 Planview of structure and associated constructed surfaces at al-Khayran. (Drawing: M. Kroot and E. Wallace, 'Assal-Dhra' Archaeological Project)

Material Culture

Stratigraphy and the Built Environment

Both phases of the structure at al-Khayran are square in shape, measuring 5 x 5m to the exterior edges of the walls and 4 x 4m in the interior (Fig. 6). Stratigraphic integrity at al-Khayran was only preserved within the interior of the structure, with a clear pattern visible in the depositional sequence of initial construction, disuse, and collapse, followed by reconstruction and renovation and eventual abandonment (Fig. 7). The earlier phase of the structure was semi-subterranean with the floor surface measuring between 0.50m and 0.15m below the Neolithic ground surface. Wall construction utilized dry-stacked limestone blocks two courses thick, with the longer straight edges of blocks used for interior and exterior surfaces and smaller stones used as filler. The floor of the earlier phase of the structure, consisting of a prepared material with a higher clay and moisture

content and fewer inclusions than surrounding deposits, was only excavated in the southeast quadrant of the structure. Two stone features inset into the floor surface, a saddle quern and sandstone slab with striations, were identified. Additional materials recovered directly on the floor surface include a carbonized bone and wood fragment submitted for radiocarbon dating and a cache of various artifacts, including knapped and ground stone tools and a mass of ground red ochre. Minimal refuse deposits were identified directly on the floor of the earlier phase of the structure.

Fig. 7 Harris matrix representation of the depositional sequence for the structure at al-Khayran. (Drawing: M. Kroot, 'Assal-Dhra' Archaeological Project)

Lying directly above the floor and cached materials of the earlier phase was a layer of wall collapse and mixed clay and silt erosional sediments devoid of artifacts. A sequence of thin layers 1-3mm thick was visible within the erosional sediments. This layer exhibited bathtubbing, with thicker deposits collecting closer to the structure's walls. On top of the collapse/ erosional layer was a second stratum, again devoid of artifacts, but with a significant amount of gravel, suggesting a different mode of transport than the underlying deposits. The top of this stratum was level, which, along with the lack of definable internal stratigraphic layers representing multiple depositional events, likely indicates that this layer was intentionally transported during renovations by the site's occupants to fill in the remaining void in the ground created by the semi-subterranean construction of earlier phase.

The later phase of the structure included the repair and reuse of the structures' southern, eastern, and western walls. Two new L-shaped wall sections were built into the structure to create a more substantial northern wall. Like those of the earlier phase of the structures, these two northern wall sections were two courses thick, with the long straight edges of the block used to create flat interior and exterior wall surfaces and the placement of smaller filler stones within construction gaps. The two L-

shaped features create a 1.65m opening in the wall, with two parallel buttresses running 1.23m into the structure's interior. The interior floor of the later phase was constructed of lime-plaster and was heavily damaged, with only small sections in each of the four corners of the structure surviving. This is unsurprising as the floor surface was identified 0.10m or less below the present-day ground surface in a locale with evidence of recent plowing. No inset stone features were identified for this later phase, but the level of preservation made this unlikely.

Fig. 8 Map of artifact density by excavation unit at al-Khayran. (Drawing: M. Kroot and E. Wallace, 'Assal-Dhra' Archaeological Project)

A flagstone surface was built between the two buttresses inside the entrance and continued at least 0.80m north of the structure. Beyond this was a cobblestone surface to the north, east, and west. Due to the poor preservation of the cobblestone surface, its extent in the early Neolithic is still being determined, but portions of the surface have been identified over 10 m north of the structure. The interior plaster and exterior flagstone surfaces were level and at the same elevation as the Neolithic ground surface on the structure's northern (downslope) edge. The cobblestone surface followed the natural slope of the ground surface. A small cache of ground stone items and hammer stones was recovered from the northwest corner of the later phase of the structure.

Fig. 9 Map of deposit depth by excavation unit at al-Khayran. (Drawing: M. Kroot and E. Wallace, 'Assal-Dhra' Archaeological Project)

While discrete depositional events were not preserved in any identifiable manner outside of the structure's walls at al-Khayran, the artifacts recovered from this context are a product of refuse disposal practices by the structure's inhabitants and are, thus, essential for understanding on-site behavior. All refuse deposits were found outside and downslope from the structure, with no *in situ* artifacts associated with exterior areas. A low density of refuse was recovered in the deposits above the later phase floor of the structure, likely transported there by the recent plowing on-site. The density of subsurface artifacts and depth of artifact-bearing deposits (Fig. 8-9) was highest to the east and west of the flagstone surface and entryway of the later phase, rapidly tapering off in both directions with units 3 m east and west of the structure returning no subsurface remains. Artifacts were recovered up to 12 m downslope of the structure, with the depth and density of deposits tapering slower in this direction. Post-depositional erosion likely played a significant role in the structure of these deposits.

Knapped Stone

6,957 knapped stone and hammer stone artifacts were excavated at al-Khayran (Table 2). The sole toolstone

Fig. 10 Examples of bidirectional blade-based formal tools recovered at al-Khayran: *A* tanged blade with edge use-wear, *B* perforator (drill), *C* borer, *D* burin. (Drawing: M. Kroot, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

Core Types	Count	% Cores
bidirectional	20	100.00%
Debitage Types	Count	% Debitage
blades	1757	28.99%
flakes	3238	53.43%
chunks	633	10.45%
chips	427	7.05%
burinations	5	0.08%
Total Debitage	6060	100.00%
Formal Tool Types	Count	% Formal Tools
lunates	1	1.85%
side-notched points or truncations	8	14.81%
tanged elongated points and knives (Jericho, Byblos, and related types)	13	24.07%
perforators (drills, borers, awls, etc.)	22	40.74%
hammer stones	10	18.52%
Total Formal Tools	54	100.00%
Informal Tool Types	Count	% Informal Tools
retouched flakes	11	1.34%
retouched blades	137	16.65%
use-wear flakes	95	11.54%
use-wear blades	497	60.39%
sickle blades	83	10.09%
Total Informal Tools	823	100.00%
Total	6957	100.00%

Table 2 Preliminary lithic analysis.

used for knapping was flint, with all the raw material variability found on-site available at a large high-quality flint outcropping 0.1km southeast of the structure. All cores recovered from the site were bidirectional. All formal tools were made from blade blanks (Fig. 10). This suggests that nearly the entirety of the assemblage derived from bidirectional knapping

(Quintero and Wilke 1995; Barzilai 2010), with some informal tools (flakes with retouch or use-wear) deriving from core preparation and/ or small-scale expedient knapping. Additionally, as noted above, all diagnostic point types recovered from subsurface deposits are typical of the PPNB, with some variation in the exact periodization typically associated with the different point forms (Gopher 1994; Shea 2013).

The cores, hammer stones, and debitage at the site attest to core preparation and reduction, as well as tool production all occurring on-site. Nineteen exhausted bidirectional cores and a single unused one, along with ten hammer stones were recovered during excavation. Production waste includes significant quantities of flakes and blades (both cortical and non-cortical), platform and façade production debitage, platform rejuvenations and façade corrections, shatter, back trimming flakes, chips, and burinations. The formal and informal tools show that a spectrum of PPNB knapped stone artifacts was being utilized at al-Khayran, including projectile points, knives, perforators (awls, drills, borers, etc.), sickles, denticulates, and blades and flakes with both use-wear and retouch (see Shea 2013 for definitions).

Fig. 11 Example ground stone artifacts recovered at al-Khayran: *A* basalt shaft straightener, *B* sandstone incised “pillow-shaped piece”, *C* basalt pestle, *D* sandstone double handstone, *E* sandstone knapped and ground disk, *F* sandstone single handstone. (Drawing: M. Kroot, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

Ground Stone

A total of ten ground stone objects were identified, eight of which were portable and two of which, as

described above, were inset into the floor of the early phase of the structure (Table 3). Items made of basalt found within refuse deposits included two broken pestles, a broken shaft straightener fragment, and a broken quern fragment. All ground stone items associated with the structure were made from sandstone. These included the inset features of the earlier phase floor, a small object with parallel grooves referred to in the literature as a pillow-shaped piece (Hermansen and Gebel 1996) lying directly on the floor of the later phase of the structure, a complete single-handed handstone and a chipped and ground flat disk, similar in form to artifacts identified as blanks for making stone rings (Gebel 2010), in association with the above-noted *in situ* cache from the early phase of the structure, and a single broken double-handed handstone fragment, which was incorporated into the later phase north wall (Fig. 11).

smooth and pierced at the umbo and a conical shell ground smooth and pierced at the apex (Fig. 12). The shell bead fragment derived from a small mother-of-pearl disc pierced at the center. Additionally, as noted above, a rounded mass of ground ochre was recovered from the cache on the floor of the earlier phase of the structure. It was likely initially held in some form of an organic container – potentially a bag, given the spherical shape of the mass – which disintegrated before recovery.

Fauna

A small and poorly preserved assemblage of fauna was recovered from al-Khayran (Table 4). A total of 84 fragments deriving from 36 individual specimens were recovered. Of these 36 specimens, 18 could be identified as ovicaprid (sheep or goat). The other 18 elements were only identifiable as medium mammals. It is possible that all remains are derived from ovicaprid individuals. The most common element was a long bone shaft fragment, and the second most common was a rib fragment. Other components include long-bone fragments identifiable to the element, a single cranial fragment, several foot and ankle bones, thoracic bones, and shoulder bones.

Earlier Phase	Count
Inset Architectural Features	
sandstone quern	1
sandstone slab with striations	1
Cached Artifacts	
complete sandstone chipped and ground flat disc	1
In Situ Artifacts	
complete sandstone single handstone	1
Later Phase	
Cached Artifacts	
complete sandstone grooved pillow-shaped piece	1
Broken Artifacts Reincorporated into Architecture	
broken sandstone double handstone	1
Refuse Context	
broken basalt pestles	2
broken basalt shaft straightener	1
broken basalt quern	1

Table 3 Preliminary ground stone analysis.

Fig. 12 Example shell beads from al-Khayran: A bivalve shell ground smooth and pierced at the umbo, B conical shell ground smooth and pierced at the apex. (Drawing: M. Kroot, ‘Assal-Dhra’ Archaeological Project)

Small Finds

Two shell beads and a shell bead fragment were recovered from refuse deposits. The two complete shell beads were a bivalve shell ground

Ovicaprids	No of Fragments
astragalus	1
femur	11
humerus	2
metacarpal	2
phalanx	2
radius	7
rib	6
scapula	2
gladiolus	1
tibia	1
zygomatic	1
Medium-sized Mammals	No of Fragments
long bone	38
rib	8
rib or vertebra	1
vertebra	1

Table 4. Faunal fragment counts by element and species.

Discussion and Conclusions

These results show that al-Khayran was occupied in at least two different episodes, with significant labor and materials expended constructing a residential structure with thick stone walls, multiple types of durable prepared surfaces, and inset architectural features. The knapped stone assemblage likely reflects a broad range of on-site activities, showing a wide array of formal tool types, the entire reduction sequence from core production through tool rejuvenation, and expedient tool use in substantial numbers. The fauna assemblage

and considerable number of sickle blades show that during their occupation of the al-Khayran site, residents enacted a variety of subsistence production and consumption activities. Overall, this behavioral reconstruction presents an occupational picture similar to that of a typical household of the agricultural village-based populations of the southern Levantine Mediterranean zone during the PPNB (Goring-Morris and Belfer-Cohen 2008). However, al-Khayran is highly unique, being the first site identified in the region with only a single solidly constructed and intensively occupied residential structure with material remains attesting to typical household function for the period.

Within the southern Levantine PPNB Mediterranean zone are several known non-village sites. However, these do not contain residential architecture as substantially and elaborately built as al-Khayran, nor do they contain the broad spectrum of material culture associated with village-based household function. Instead, they tend to serve such roles as mortuary (Goring-Morris 1991) and ritual (Bar-Yosef and Alon 1988) sites or to be the location of specialized economic activities, such as flint mining (Quintero 1994) or seasonal hunting (Alhaique and Gopher 2005). Small sites are also found in the more arid regions bordering on the southern Levantine Mediterranean zone in the south (*e.g.*, Ronen *et al.* 2001) and east (*e.g.*, Fujii 2013). However, these sites are dissimilar to al-Khayran in form, content, and function – the most notable difference being the use of circular residential architecture across the desert zones of the Southern Levant. Additionally, many sites contain no or minimally elaborated residential architecture (Goring-Morris 1993; Garrard *et al.* 1994), while those that do contain extensively built architecture are far larger in scale than al-Khayran (Henry *et al.* 2003; Fujii 2013).

Further analysis of al-Khayran can help us understand the settlement systems, subsistence production practices, and economic relations that underpin the unique results from the site within its broader regional context during the development of agricultural village-based life. There are two possible interpretations of al-Khayran: (1) a small farmstead for a single residential unit or (2) an agricultural field house occupied by a village-based residential unit. The first of these, a small farmstead, would suggest that there was a greater diversity of residential behaviors in the southern Levantine Mediterranean zone than previously documented, with at least some settlement decisions being driven by the labor demands developing during the shift towards agriculturally-based subsistence systems (Demangeon 1962; Chisholm 1979; Stone 1996). If al-Khayran is a field house, it would also broaden our picture of residential

behavior in the PPNB. However, it would also suggest a tension between the logistics of emergent agricultural economies and the relations of production that underpin them.

In certain circumstances, field house usage can enable the benefits of settlement aggregation and dispersal (Sutton 1977; Moore 1979; Preucel 1990). By practicing dual residence mobility (Preucel 1990), producers can develop landesque capital that facilitates in-field intensification practices, including shelter and residential facilities that enable producers to inhabit farm fields during periods of high labor inputs, while also having access to population aggregations that can provide access to other resources that facilitate further intensification. Socially, field houses are associated with resource competition (Kohler 1992), as they materially mark control over land-based resources and also facilitate the presence of producers in-field to enforce land tenure claims (Stone 1994).

Ultimately, resolving the role that al-Khayran played in the settlement systems of the west-central Transjordanian PPNB will allow us to understand better the social and material pressures that drove residential and economic practices in the period. Whatever the specific behaviors, al-Khayran does show that residential practices and communities were more varied than previously known for the PPNB. The question is, is this variability a product of (1) space, mobility, and the logistics of subsistence production, (2) the relations of production under agriculture, or (3) both as interlinked developmental processes?

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